

Retrieval of Elastic Constants of Liquid Crystals Using Physics-Informed Neural Network

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Abstract: A novel approach to retrieve the elastic constants of a nematic liquid crystal based on physics-informed deep neural network is proposed. © 2022 The Author(s)

1. Electro-optical effect in nematic liquid crystals

Nematic liquid crystals (NLCs) are characterized by a huge electro-optical effect, exploited in several fundamental photonic applications such as displays, tunable waveplates, spatial light modulator for beam shaping, and temporal pulse shaping. Essentially, in the nematic mesophase the molecular distribution features a high degree of orientational order, with the local alignment being modelled by a point-dependent vectorial field called the director [1, 2]. When an electric field is applied through the NLC film, a dipole is generated in the molecules. The induced dipole then interacts with the external field, tending to align the external field. Such alignment process is counteracted by inter-molecular interaction, macroscopically modelled as an elastic energy (Frank-Oseen continuum theory). Here, we consider a planar NLC with the director \hat{n} at rest being oriented along the NLC-glass interface, this direction is named \hat{x} . The geometry of the sample of thickness L is shown in Fig. 1(a). An overall voltage difference V is applied to the cell, thus inducing rotations only on the plane xz . The local quasi-static potential is denoted by $V(z)$. The director is then univocally determined by the angle θ , the latter being defined as the angle formed by the director \hat{n} with \hat{x} . The boundary condition -assuming strong anchoring- for θ is set as $\theta(z=0) = \theta(z=L) = \theta_B$. Starting from the Frank-Oseen continuum theory, the equilibrium distribution of the director is then determined by the following system [2, 3]

$$(K_3 \sin^2 \theta + K_1 \cos^2 \theta) \frac{d^2 \theta}{dz^2} + \frac{K_3 - K_1}{2} \sin(2\theta) \left(\frac{d\theta}{dz} \right)^2 + \frac{\Delta \epsilon}{2} \sin(2\theta) \left(\frac{dV}{dz} \right)^2 = 0, \quad (1)$$

$$(\epsilon_{\parallel} \sin^2 \theta + \epsilon_{\perp} \cos^2 \theta) \frac{d^2 V}{dz^2} + \Delta \epsilon \sin(2\theta) \frac{d\theta}{dz} \frac{dV}{dz} = 0. \quad (2)$$

The elastic forces arising in the material under external torque(s), with K_1 and K_3 accounting for splay and bend deformations, respectively is modelled by Equation (1). Equation (2) is the Poisson equation rewritten for an inhomogeneous uniaxial dielectric featured by the two absolute dielectric constants ϵ_{\parallel} (parallel to the director) and ϵ_{\perp} (normal to the director).

2. Physics-Informed Neural Network applied to NLC reorientation

These days Deep Learning (DL) is successfully used as an alternative numerical tool to more established methods, especially when DL is *coupled* with the physics of the system, both for forward and inverse problems. The latter approach is broadly called as scientific machine learning or physics-informed machine learning (PINN) [4], and it is realized by adding an additional cost (or loss) provided by the substitution of the temporary results into the original equation. Theoretically speaking, PINN leverages the fact that a deep neural network (DNN) acts as a universal function approximator. DNNs, together with the application of automatic differentiation to the back propagation in DNN, led to the recent development of mesh-free PINNs for the solution of partial differential equations.

With respect to the electro-optical effect in NLCs, the main practical problem is to accurately measure the mechanical (elastic constants) and electrical properties of the mixture [5]. Indeed, the electro-optical effect is so strong that even a small error in determining the NLC constants yields strong variation in the phase retardation imparted by the NLC cell on the optical field. Furthermore, different set-up need to be used for measuring all the

Fig. 1. **a** Schematic illustration of the liquid crystal cell with planar alignment to which a voltage V is applied. **b** Predicting the solutions of the coupled PDE $\theta(z)$ and $V(z)$ when a fixed voltage $V = 2.86\text{V}$ is applied to the LC cell. **c** Inverse prediction of the elastic constants and permittivity of the LC.

NLC parameters. Finally, from the technological point of view the finite fabrication accuracy (on the cell thickness and on the pre-tilt angle, mainly) constrains us to use most of the times local measurements to calibrate the NLC device. Here, our aim is to use PINN to invert the NLC reorientation problem given by Eqs. (1-2) starting from a simple optical measurement of the phase retardation versus the applied voltage. The PINN approach permits to account for several parameters together, thus permitting the best-fitting between the theory and the experiments. To start, we collect synthetic data by numerically simulating Eqs. (1-2) for fixed values of K_1 and K_3 and various input voltages. A typical data set is shown in Fig 1(b). We first train a deep neural network (DNN) to solve the forward problem, i.e. to solve the system of Eqs. (1-2). We select six data points from our numerical simulation and train the DNN to find the solution versus z for a given voltage V . The results are shown in Fig. 1(b). A very good accuracy is achieved after a training period of 15000 epochs. Next, we solve the inverse problem in order to predict the NLC parameters. The physics part of the PINN can take N different couples of θ and V values for training, indexed by the applied voltage V . The physics loss is now a linear combination of the N losses; such a combined loss is then back-propagated until a stationary value is obtained (together with minimization of the total loss) for the NLC physical parameters K_1 , K_3 and ϵ_{\perp} . The results of the inverse prediction for PINNs with varying N are shown in Fig 1(c). The prediction of the elastic and permittivity constants can be improved by properly choosing the learning rate, the number of voltage points as well as the weight of the backpropagated losses.

3. Conclusions

In conclusion, we developed a novel method based on physics-informed deep learning to retrieve the physical constants of liquid crystals necessary to characterize the giant electro-optical effects in NLCs.

References

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